

Social and Emotional Skills and Professional Identity as Predictors of Job Satisfaction of Teachers

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Abstract:- This study determined the social and emotional skills and professional identity as predictors of job satisfaction. The quantitative approach using the correlational technique and analysis was utilized in this study with a sample of 300 teachers coming from the Public Elementary Schools of Manay District, Davao oriental Division. Sets of adapted survey questionnaires were used to obtain data from the respondents, which were subjected to content validity and reliability analysis. The data were analyzed using the Mean, Pearson-r, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The results reveal that the levels of social and emotional skills were rated high, and professional identity was rated v high. While job satisfaction was also rated high. Moreover, a significant relationship existed between these variables. A significant relationship between social and emotional skills and job satisfaction of teachers was significant. There is a significant the influence of social and emotional skills, and professional identity on the job satisfaction of teachers. However, However, professional identity emerged as a significant predictor of job satisfaction of teachers.

Keywords:- Educational Management, Servant Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Teachers' Efficacy. Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

On the other hand, discontentment with one's job may stem from an inadequate balance between work and personal life, limited prospects for growth and development, an unsupportive work environment, insufficient encouragement, lack of acknowledgement, and excessive stress. These factors can also contribute to a higher rate of employee turnover (Mulyanti, Purnama, & Pawinanto). Consequently, dissatisfied employees may experience a decrease in their performance and productivity, and they may either undermine the work or quit the job altogether (Mira, Choon, & Thim, 2019). Dissatisfied workers tend to depart the organization and may demoralize other employees prior to their departure (Barkhuizen & Gumede, 2021).

Teachers have an necessary function in building the financial structure of our economic system so the duty of state to encourage teachers for their occupation through incentive or extraordinary enticement (Meitisari, Hanafi, & Wahab, 2018). Level of employee delight is one of the methods that make the agency successful. The success of schooling device relies upon on the contribution of teachers (Yuen, Loh, Zhou, & Wong, 2018). They are the principal

source of any society for encouraging the country bringing the kids and childhood of any nation towards high quality as properly as prosperous sides. Teachers come to be upset if they are now not compensating with appreciation, recognition, security, salary, and self-respect (Tahir, 2019).

There is records that suggests emotional intelligence has an affect on employees' job satisfaction. Understanding interpersonal feelings can resource in the legislation of poor feelings and emotions, which can enhance a person's overall performance at work and lay the groundwork for job happiness. It appears that workers People with strong emotional intelligence will be happier in their employment because they can identify and lessen feelings of hopelessness and stress. (Rafsanjani, Nursyamsi, & Pono, 2019). Suharto, Suyanto, and Hendri, (2019) located that teachers expert identity ought to mirror their expert lives and career decision-making. Some empirical research confirmed that professional identity used to be related with career satisfaction, Diaz-Fernandez, Pasamar-Reyes, & Valle-Cabrera (2017) performed lookup in Turkey to explore elements influencing the turnover intention of nurses; their research determined that nurse professional identity ought to affect their job satisfaction.

It is on the above context that the researcher would like to determine the influence of social and emotional skills and professional identity of instructors on the relationship between job pride in college organizations. As such, involved beneficiaries may locate the learn about as a beneficial capability in coming up with the feasible solutions for related problems. Through tremendous readings of a number literatures, the researchers located the substantial relationships between the three variables (Denson, Loveday, & Dalton 2010; Denissen, Geenen, Soto, John, & van Aken, 2020). However, most of these studies had been conducted internationally and did not especially study the affect of social and emotional abilities and expert identity of instructors on the relationship between job satisfaction, which is the high problem of this study, making this thesis a contribution to the literature for nearby putting and a skill for the technology of new understanding.

The thrust of this study is to find out the relationship between the social and emotional skills on the relationship between professional identity on job satisfaction. More specifically, this study endeavored to determine the following objectives. The first objective is to describe level of emotional and social skills of teachers in terms of self-control, persistence, academic competence, social

competence; and mastery orientation, subsequent is to ascertain the stage of expert identification teachers in terms of information of the profession, philosophy of the profession, professional roles and expertise, attitude, engagement behavior, and interaction. The 1/3 one is to confirm the level of job pleasure of teachers in phrases of security, work environment, job responsibilities, and neighborhood attachment. To verify the substantial affiliation between teachers' job happiness and emotional and social abilities, a professional identity and job pleasure of teachers and which of the two independent variables extensively predicts the job pride of teachers. The following null hypotheses were tested at the significant level of 0.05 ; There are no significant relationships between, emotional and social skills and job satisfaction of teachers, professional identity and job satisfaction of teachers. None of the independent variables significantly predicts job satisfaction of teachers

➤ *Review of Related Literature*

This segment presents discussions on the fundamental principles, notions, thoughts, and perspectives from diverse writers who have contributed valuable insights on the autonomous variable, which is social and emotional proficiency, emphasizing on the orientation of mastery (Trends, 2014). On the other hand, professional identity highlights engagement behavior knowledge, professional knowledge, attitude towards professional roles and expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional ethics, and interaction (Auxier, Hughes & Kline, 2003; Nelson & Jackson, 2003). Meanwhile, the contentment of teachers with their job focuses on security (salary, benefits, performance rewards, recognition, promotion), work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachment. (Zainala, Sagalaa, & Muhamadb, 2015).

➤ *Social and Emotional Skills*

The quality of the relationship and social interactions between teachers and students play a crucial role in the cognitive, social, and affective-motivational development of students (Denissen, Luhmann, Chung, & Bleidorn, 2019). However, when students violate rules, create noise, disrupt instruction, show disengagement or lack of focus, teachers often experience negative feelings and find it challenging to maintain positive relationships with them (Abrahams, Pancorbo, Primi, Santos, Kyllonen, John, & De Fruyt, 2019).

In the long term, the inability of teachers to interact and establish connections with students effectively and their feelings of anger or anxiety are associated with decreased occupational well-being (Duckworth, Taxer, Eskreis-Winkler, Galla, & Gross, 2019). Furthermore, teachers who feel emotionally drained tend to be less sensitive and provide less emotional support in their interactions with students, leading to lower motivation and achievement in their classes (Denissen, Geenen, Soto, John, & van Aken, 2020).

Hence, it is crucial to identify the attributes of educators that aid them in managing their own emotions and fostering favorable teacher-student relationships, even in trying social encounters with pupils, which is pertinent for the growth of students and the well-being of teachers. In this respect,

experts have stressed the pivotal role of teachers' social-emotional proficiency for more than a decade (Farrell & Vaillancourt, 2020).

Nevertheless, as there is a scarcity of unbiased appraisal instruments that are specifically tailored to meet the vocational requirements of teachers, it remains challenging to empirically probe the types of knowledge and competencies that teachers must acquire, such as those obtained in teacher training and professional development programs, to excel in dealing with social and emotional hurdles in the school milieu (Bayram Ozdemir, Ozdemir, & Boersma, 2021).

➤ *Professional Identity of Teachers*

Building a teacher's persona is a significant aspect of ensuring their dedication to their job and compliance with professional standards. The persona a teacher develops shapes their attitudes, where they focus their efforts, how they seek professional growth opportunities, and the responsibilities they see as inherent to their role (Cureton, Davis, & Giegerich, 2019).

Teachers' identity development is influenced by their views on teaching and learning (Mariotti, McAuliffe, Grothaus, West-Olatunji, & Snow, 2019). Hence, it is essential for teachers to consciously examine their beliefs and bring them to the forefront of their consciousness (Murphy, Jorgensen, & Olson, 2020) by reflecting on their practice during the induction period. As teachers reflect, their sense of identity plays a vital role in their understanding of their actions. Although reflection is a powerful way for students and teachers to explore their teaching identities, there is little information about how a teacher's identity evolves early in their career, which is a critical gap in our understanding of teaching (Person, Garner, Ghoston, & Petersen, 2020).

Furthermore, teacher professional identity is challenging to define (Widodo, Fang, & Elyas, 2020), and researchers conceptualize identity in various ways depending on their philosophical perspective and analytical framework through which they examine aspects of identity. In most studies, identity refers to a teacher's self-perception in a social context. (Bahrami, Zabardast, & Salimi, 2020). interpretation of personal stories (Hanna, Oostdam, Severiens, & Zijlstra, 2020), teachers' roles and teacher narrative and discourse (Janke, Bloom, Boyce, Johnson, Kopacek, O'Sullivan, & Ross, 2021).

➤ *Job Satisfaction*

Job contentment or dissatisfaction arises from how employees perceive their job in terms of fulfilling their important and necessary needs (Daniel, 2019). Lei, Basit, and Hassan (2018) define job satisfaction as the level of contentment an individual has with their job, while Lima and Allida (2021) argue that it is based on a person's emotional connection to their job.

To achieve job satisfaction and positive outcomes, supervisors must adapt their leadership approach to involve employees in decision-making processes, increasing their commitment to the company's objectives. This involves

involving as many employees as possible, supporting individual and team efforts, and sharing information throughout the organization to motivate employees. Effective supervisors work both vertically and horizontally, managing cross-functional processes, projects, time, and resources (Omar, Rafie, & Ahmad Selo, 2020).

Therefore, organizations seek employees with strong work ethics, who are hardworking, reliable, and put in significant effort. There are four broad categories of work ethics theories, as well as more specific and concrete theories about job satisfaction (Rafsanjani, Nursyamsi, & Pono, 2019).

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

As shown in figure 1, the independent variables of this study are social and emotional skills, professional identity and job satisfactions.

of five levels, with the most basic needs at the bottom and the most complex needs at the top. This hierarchy starts with physiological needs, such as food and shelter, followed by safety needs, social needs, esteem needs, and finally self-actualization needs. According to Maslow, individuals must satisfy their lower-level needs before they can move up to the next level. Once all five levels are satisfied, individuals can achieve their full potential and experience a sense of fulfillment in life. This theory has been widely accepted and applied in various fields, such as business, education, and psychology.

This study was anchored on different theories based on the assumed relationship shown. First, it was anchored on the theory of Weiss (2009) who said that awareness of are better equipped to handle interpersonal conflicts and communicate effectively with colleagues and superiors. This ultimately leads to a more positive work environment and stronger relationships within the team. appear to be happier at work because they can more easily recognize and reduce feelings of hopelessness and stress. Furthermore, Dalton (2010) found that while teachers with higher emotional intelligence had an advantage in terms of life satisfaction, job satisfaction was only one part of the larger concept of life satisfaction. discovered. The results of Thomas and Tram (2006) suggest that teachers' emotional intelligence is significantly positively correlated with job performance.

Similarly, recognizing interpersonal emotions can help control negative feelings and emotions, enabling individuals to perform better at work. Improved performance is, in turn, the basis for job satisfaction. Employees with high emotional intelligence are more likely to recognize and reduce feelings of hopelessness and stress, and are therefore more likely to be satisfied with their jobs (Capkun, Hameri & Weiss, 2009). Moreover, teachers with higher emotional intelligence have good levels of life satisfaction, but job satisfaction is only one part of the larger concept of life satisfaction. The results of Thomas, Tram, and Linda (2006) suggest that teachers' emotional intelligence is significantly positively correlated with job performance. (Denson, Loveday, & Dalton, 2010).

Moreover, emotional skills affect Satisfaction with work is influenced by interpersonal and intrapersonal emotional management, as well as improved performance. Increased job satisfaction is a result of better performance. It is believed that employees with higher emotional intelligence experience greater job satisfaction, as they are able to control negative emotions and stress effectively. Furthermore, job satisfaction is a key factor in overall life satisfaction. Lower levels of job stress are linked to increased job satisfaction (Pittau, Zelli, & Gelman, 2009).

Similarly, the metacognitive attitudes of teachers are strong predictors of effective teaching motivation. This finding supports the research of Purnama (2020), which emphasizes that teachers' beliefs in their ability to manage classroom situations, instructional tasks, and interpersonal relationships with colleagues strongly affect their satisfaction with job conditions and, ultimately, the morale of the entire school. This is evident from the aggregated job satisfaction levels of teachers (Sopiah, Kamaludin, Sangadji, & Narmaditya, 2021).

If the employees are content, they would deliver exceptional quality performance within the optimal time and result in expanding profits. Pleased teachers are also more likely to be imaginative and inventive and develop innovative ideas that enable an establishment to grow and positively evolve with time and shifting market conditions. The quality or efficiency of teachers is deemed to be linked with their contentment towards their profession and values. Therefore, it is evident that an effective and proficient teacher will achieve the desired learning outcomes, provided they are content in their profession or job (Wright & Crapanzano 2007).

In Tang's (2020) research, rural teachers in the Chinese mainland were taken as the research subject, and a two-level model was adopted to investigate the moderating effect of teachers' professional identity on their job satisfaction. The results verified that long working hours, large class size, and low awareness of income status are significantly associated with low job satisfaction, whereas teachers' professional identity can alleviate the adverse effects of working hours and income.

Regarding the actual work, due to the online format, teachers frequently encounter technical glitches during their videoconference sessions, which generally makes them feel that the work task is increasingly arduous, and the work pressure is progressively mounting. The skills that teachers possess are insufficient to solve these issues, which causes them to become more and more discontented with work. The inability to release tension for such a prolonged duration can easily lead to a decline in professional identity for teachers (Reidhead, 2020).

Over time, teachers are prone to insomnia, tension, irritability, fatigue, and other negative emotions, resulting in varying degrees of job burnout. When the degree of teachers' job burnout is more serious, it is easier to have a poor implementation of teaching activities and affect the order [6].

In the long run, it will affect the normal operation of university teaching, especially in the current unique situation (Lima, & Allida, 2021; Leung, & Lin, 2022).

Meanwhile, findings from numerous studies have demonstrated that those who experience less workplace stress have better levels of job satisfaction. Researchers have also discovered that those with more social and emotional intelligence had better levels of life satisfaction, with job satisfaction constituting only a minor part of the overall idea of life pleasure. The results of Loan (2020) suggested that identity of teacher has a significant positive relationship with their job performance. Furthermore, satisfied teachers offer higher to be utilized by school heads and teachers in enhancing the quality of their instruction and providing better support for their students, as well as increasing their job commitment and reducing teacher turnover. The knowledge of emotional and social skills can also improve job satisfaction, which is crucial in addressing teacher shortage and improving the overall status of the teaching profession. Therefore, the recommendations of this study can be valuable not only to the education sector but also to future researchers who may want to explore the relationship between social and emotional skills and job satisfaction among teachers.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ *Participants*

The study was conducted in Manay District, Province of Davao Oriental from June 2020 to May 2022. Region XI or popularly known as referred to the valley of municipality. This research involved a total of 375 educators who responded to the survey. To surpass the maximum sample of 300 from Slovin's formula, the researchers decided to increase the sample size by 75. The objective of the researchers is to ensure that there is enough allowance for the number of participants. To select the participants, a different probability sampling technique such as a cluster or simple random sampling was utilized for each population stratum (Thomas, 2022).

For the study, the participants must be teachers who are currently teaching in a public school in Manay District and have at least one year of teaching experience. They also need to sign a Certificate of Consent Form before joining the research. Those who are not qualified are teachers who are teaching in private schools, on leave, withdrew from the study, holding administrative positions, or have less than a year of teaching experience in the public school. Participants

4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The measure is always evident among public secondary school teachers.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The measure frequently evident among public secondary school teachers
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The measure is sometimes evident among public secondary school teachers.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The measure is seldomly evident among public secondary school teachers.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This measure is not evident among public secondary school teachers

.A team of experts validated the four sets of questionnaires before approval. The construct validity of the instruments had an overall score of 4.0, indicating that the tools are well-liked. The alpha coefficient for social and emotional skills, is .911. professional identity is .887, and job

who manipulated or provided considerably incomplete data and did not signify their intention to join the research through the certificate of consent form were also excluded. Participants can withdraw from the study at any time without giving any justification. The researcher observed that teachers in Davao Oriental lack teamwork, empathy, and support from the administration. Due to the pandemic, teachers are faced with too many roles, resulting in poor work behaviors that hinder progress and development in the organization.

This study used three (3) instruments to address the research problems. The researchers collected primary data, which was divided into three sections: the participants' experience regarding social and emotional skills, professional identity, and job satisfaction. The survey questionnaires used in the study were gathered from similar studies. The instrument was restructured to make it more appropriate to current and local settings. The instrument was e validated by five (5) professional validators to make it more applicable 12 and credible and received an acceptable rating. Pilot testing will be carried out after validation. Cronbach's alpha will be used to test the survey's validity. The closer Cronbach's alpha coefficient is to 1.0, the stronger the internal consistency of the scale's items, according to Gliem (2003). The first questionnaire measured experienced social and emotional skills which focuses on self-control, persistence, mastery coordination, academic self-worth, and social capability, an adopted questionnaire on Resource Source Table for Original Items Used in the Tauck Family Foundation Formative Assessment Tools (2014). The second questionnaire measure's professional identity based on the study of knowledge of the engagement behaviors, knowledge of the profession, attitude professional roles & expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional values and interaction (Auxier, Hughes & Kline, 2003; Nelson & Jackson, 2003). The third questionnaire, questionnaire deal with job satisfaction with emphasis on the following indicators: security (salary, benefits, rewards performance, recognition, promotion) work environment; job responsibilities; and community attachments/ linkages. The questionnaire is modified and patterned on the study of Asia Pacific Institute of Advanced Research (APIAR) (2017). The scales used to interpret experienced social and emotional skills, professional identity, and job satisfaction are as follows.

➤ *Range of Means Descriptive Equivalent Description*

satisfaction Alpha coefficient is .912. Using the coefficient alpha has the benefit of producing results that are simple to understand.

➤ *Research Design and Procedure*

This study used a non-experimental quantitative research design that used the descriptive correlational research technique to collect data, thoughts, facts, and information relevant to the subject. Descriptive non-experimental correlational design controlled the extent of a relationship between two or more variables (Goertzen, 2017). In this study, the correlation method is the best design to meet the study's objectives and determine whether the hypothesis is accepted. Now, if the significance value is greater than .05, H_0 is accepted and H_a is accepted. Hypothesis testing determines if the correlations can be strong or weak (Creswell & Poth, 2012).

The initial step in data gathering was asking permission from the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of Mindanao, also with the Deped Division of Davao Oriental, as well as the different schools of Manay District to allow the researcher to conduct the study. Upon approval, the researcher traveled to different schools in the Manay District to personally handed the approved letter with google form links to the questionnaires. The researcher was very grateful for the positive responses among schools from the Department of Education of the Deped Division of Davao Oriental.

Due to the pandemic's health requirements, the questionnaire was distributed online through the Google Form platform. The link to the Google Form was distributed to several groups through Facebook Messenger, and school research coordinators assisted the researchers in disseminating the google links to the teachers. On the hand, to guarantee that there would be 375 responses, the survey was kept open for at least one month. The study's collection of data started in the fourth week of January 2022 and was completed in February 2022. To determine the significance of the relationship between the variable, Pearson-r was used. Furthermore, regression analysis identifies the factors that predict the outcome variable based on the list of predictor variables. The investigation assessed whether proficient social and emotional abilities and vocational identity have a significant impact on job contentment. Lastly, regression analysis was employed to examine and establish the degree of influence. Conversely, the investigator adhered to the ethical guidelines throughout the research by following the protocol assessments and standardized criteria established by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) with certification number 2022-013. The participants were provided with the opportunity to voluntarily and freely participate in the study without incurring any expenses.. Additionally, following the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher ensured that the respondents' private information was kept secret. The researcher also ensured that the information gleaned from the survey questions was correct and that the sources of the information were acknowledged correctly. Overall, 16 before, during, and after the study, the researcher adhered to all ethical standards established by UMER.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the data collected from the teachers on experience social and emotional skills, and professional identity significantly influence job satisfaction is given, evaluated, and interpreted in light of the research objectives.

➤ *Level of Social and Emotional Skills of Teachers*

Table presents the mean values of social and emotional competence indicators for teachers, as depicted in Table 1. The overall mean score of 4.12 is considered very high, with a standard deviation of 0.412 and a descriptive interpretation of high. The respondents' high ratings may have contributed to this elevated level.

Table 1 *Level of Social and Emotional Skills of Teachers*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-control	0.28	4.39	Very High
Persistence	0.30	4.26	Very High
Mastery Orientation	0.31	4.02	High
Academic Self-efficacy	0.31	4.01	High
Social Competence	0.37	3.87	High
Overall	0.19	4.12	High

Indicates that the level of social and emotional skills of teachers is always manifested among public school teachers. The first indicator with the highest mean is self-control, with a mean rating of 4.39, with a descriptive level of very high. The second is persistence, with a mean rating of 4.26, mastery orientation with a mean of 4.04, academic self-efficacy, 4.01 which is described as very high. Lastly is social competence, with a mean rating of 3.87, which is described as high got the lowest mean rating.

The elevated level is obtained from the feedback, which all indicate high levels. The signals, including self-discipline, tenacity, proficiency orientation, intellectual self-confidence, and interpersonal skills, receive high appraisals. Empirical data from field research suggests that social and emotional proficiencies have a pivotal function in regulating academic performance, employability, and welfare. This demonstrates that the scholar has opted to strive towards their objectives, notwithstanding hindrances, complexities, or frustrations. For persistence to be present, the learner's conduct should be self-initiated and indicate an underlying steadfastness to persevere with the mission or objective, notwithstanding the possibility of setbacks along the way.

In addition, this result is (Chien, Harbin, Goldhagen, Lippman, & Walker, 2019; Farrell, & Vaillancourt, 2020). Make sure that self-discipline demonstrates the ability of students to regulate their emotions and behavior, discourage negative behavior, focus on specific tasks, and wait their turn to get what they want. . A study by Bandy & Moore (2010) found that the ability to control emotions and behavior prevents negative reactions and delays gratification. Moffitt (2011) showed that self-discipline helps children stay focused

and focused on their work. The fact that researchers argued that academic success requires self-discipline as much as intelligence.

➤ *Level of Professional Identity of Teachers*

The second aim of the study was to assess the extent of teachers' professional identity using a questionnaire that gauged their understanding of engagement behaviors, professional knowledge, attitudes towards professional roles and expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional values, and interactions (Auxier, Hughes & Kline, 2003; Nelson & Jackson, 2003).

The results in Table 2 present the findings on the level of professional identity among teachers. The analysis indicates a high grand mean of 4.07, with a standard deviation of 0.29, signifying that the manifestation of teachers' professional identity is intermittent.

Table 2 *Level of Professional Identity of Teachers*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Knowledge of the Profession	0.34	4.05	High
Philosophy of the Profession	0.33	4.02	High
Professional Roles and Expertise	0.43	4.03	High
Attitude	0.41	4.13	High
Engagement Behaviors	0.56	4.15	High
Interaction	0.47	4.01	High
Overall	0.29	4.07	High

The first indicator with the highest mean is engagement behaviors, with a mean rating of 4.15, with a descriptive level of high. The second is attitude, with a mean rating of 4.13, which is still high, knowledge of the profession, 4.05, professional roles and expertise, 4.03, philosophy of the profession, 4.02. Lastly is interaction, with a mean rating of 4.01, which is described as high got the lowest mean rating still high.

The professional identity of teachers, which was highly rated by respondents, indicates that teachers need a transparent self-image that is essential for the counseling profession to thrive. Refers to a set of beliefs, values, and assumptions about different characteristics of different, chosen professions.

This assumption is similar to work by Widodo et al., (2020) and Uuen et al., (2018). They argue that for guidance professionals to be successful, they need to be clear about their identity. Indicates that it is important. Professional identity refers to the set of beliefs, values, and assumptions about the specific characteristics that distinguish a person's chosen profession from others. Moreover, expertise leads to strong professional identities with a wide range of expertise. Teachers are expected to process and assess new knowledge required for core professional practice and to update the

knowledge base regularly to improve practice and meet new educational needs.

➤ *Level of Job Satisfaction of Teachers*

Presented in Table 4 is the level of job satisfaction of teachers in terms of security (Salary, Benefits, Rewards Performance, Recognition, Promotion); work environment; Job responsibilities; and community attachment. It registered an overall mean rating of 3.99, which is high. This indicates that the level of job satisfaction of teachers is oftentimes manifested among public school teachers. The first indicator with the highest mean is community attachments/linkages, with a mean rating of 4.11, with a descriptive level of high. The second is security, with a mean rating of 3.97, which is described as very high. Lastly is work environment and job responsibilities with a mean rating of 3.94, which is described as high got the lowest mean rating. The high level of job satisfaction, as rated by the respondents, These indicators registered an overall very high rating which was the product of the very high scores rated by the teachers. Of all the indicators, morale in the school dominates that yielded the highest mean score among the indicators.

This indicates that every teacher must have the potential and clear intention to discharge their duty with utmost devotion to derive satisfaction from their work. Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves. Any work cannot be effectively done without satisfaction Different authors' perspectives Murphy et al., (2020); Mulyanti et al., who said that that teacher job satisfaction is the sense of accomplishment and pride felt by those who enjoy their work and do well. increase.

Table 3 *Level of Job Satisfaction of Teachers*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Security	0.30	3.97	High
Work Environment	0.30	3.94	High
Job Responsibilities	0.28	3.94	High
Community Attachments/Linkages	0.35	4.11	High
Overall	0.26	3.99	High

Job satisfaction is also the extent to which a job provides workers with satisfaction, fulfillment and enjoyment. Job satisfaction is also used to indicate how satisfied teachers are with meeting their career goals and expectations.

➤ *Significance on the Relationship between Social and Emotional Skills and Job Satisfaction of Teachers*

The primary aim of this research was to determine whether social and emotional aptitudes have a significant correlation with the job satisfaction levels of teachers. The results of the calculations have been presented in Table 4 As per the table, the overall r-value for the correlation between the social and emotional skills and job satisfaction levels of teachers is 0.218, with a probability value of $p < 0.05$. Since

the p-value is lower than 0.05, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between social and emotional skills and job satisfaction of teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. All the indicators of social and emotional skills, when compared with job satisfaction levels of teachers, have R values with p values less than 0.05, thereby indicating significance.

Specifically, when the indicators of self-control are correlated with the indicators of job satisfaction having a correlation coefficient of .145 and a p value of .012, hence significant. Moreover, when the indicators of persistence are correlated with the indicator of job satisfaction having a

correlation coefficient of .330 and a p value of .330, hence significant. When the indicators of mastery orientation, academic self-efficacy, and social competence are correlated with the indicators of job satisfaction having a correlation coefficient of .145 and a p value of .012, hence significant. Moreover, when the indicators of persistence are correlated with the indicator of job satisfaction having a correlation coefficient of .330 and a p value of .330, were found significant. Mastery orientation having a correlation coefficient of .041, academic self-efficacy having a correlation coefficient of .087, and social competence having a correlation coefficient of .083 were found to be not significant at a 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4 Significance on the Relationship between Social and Emotional Skills and Job Satisfaction of Teachers

Social and Emotional Skills	Job Satisfaction				
	Security	Work Environment	Job Responsibilities	Community Attachments	Overall
Self-control	.135*	.069	.178**	.122*	.145*
	.019	.232	.002	.036	.012
Persistence	.206**	.331**	.282**	.313**	.330**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Mastery Orientation	.076	.164**	-.001	-.078	.041
	.188	.005	.982	.179	.481
Academic Self-efficacy	.103	.188**	.029	-.007	.087
	.075	.001	.616	.909	.132
Social Competence	.112	.168**	.011	.004	.083
	.054	.004	.843	.942	.150
Overall	.203**	.301**	.152**	.107	.218**
	.000	.000	.008	.065	.000

The current investigation indicates a noteworthy association between the social and emotional competencies of educators and their job satisfaction. This implies that social and emotional competencies significantly impact the job satisfaction of teachers, as demonstrated by the information. This aligns with Bahrami's (2020) findings, which suggest that social and emotional competencies play a role in teachers' overall job satisfaction, as measured by self-reports. The evidence is supported by the fact that social and emotional competencies involve the capacity to recognize one's own and others' emotions, self-motivate, and effectively regulate one's own and others' emotions, resulting in reduced burnout and increased job satisfaction. Consequently, job satisfaction might be higher.

➤ Significance on the Influence of Professional Identity and Job Satisfaction of Teachers

And job satisfaction of teachers. The results of this study, displayed in Table 5, demonstrate a strong positive correlation between professional identity and job satisfaction, with an overall coefficient of correlation of .797 and a p-value less than 0.05. This significant degree of correlation indicates that the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between professional identity and job

satisfaction of teachers in public elementary schools can be rejected.

Furthermore, the study found that certain indicators of professional identity, such as knowledge of the profession, were correlated with job satisfaction factors like security, work environment, and job responsibilities. However, other indicators of professional identity, such as attitude towards professional roles and expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional values, and interaction, were more strongly correlated with job satisfaction, yielding overall r-values of .127, .745, .689, .694, and .697, respectively, with p-values less than 0.05.

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of professional identity in shaping teachers' job satisfaction and underscores the need for continued research in this area to further understand the complex relationship between the two. As the teaching profession continues to evolve, it is essential to identify and support the personal characteristics that contribute to teachers' satisfaction and fulfillment in their work. of teachers. Some recent research on teacher identity development (Sopiah, et al., 2021) explores how personal and professional

Table 5 Significance on the Relationship between Professional Identity and Job Satisfaction of Teachers

Professional Identity	Job Satisfaction				
	Security	Work Environment	Job Responsibilities	Community Attachments	Overall
Knowledge of Profession	.121*	.093	.009	.018	.069
	.037	.109	.879	.753	.237
Philosophy of Profession	.140*	.198**	.036	.067	.127*
	.015	.001	.536	.251	.028
Professional Roles & Expertise	.746**	.552**	.586**	.669**	.745**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Attitude	.609**	.623**	.522**	.613**	.689**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Engagement Behaviors	.633**	.593**	.527**	.624**	.694**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Interaction	.647**	.576**	.584**	.537**	.679**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.762**	.691**	.609**	.677**	.797**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Selves evolve over the course of a teacher's career to be negotiated. It advocates an interactive perspective on understanding what to do. A teacher's sense of professional identity is thought to be manifested in changes in job satisfaction, professional engagement, self-efficacy, and motivation levels (Hermans & Hermans-Konopka, 2010).

➤ *Significance of Influence of Independent Variables on the Job Satisfaction of Teachers*

Presented in Table 6 is the significance of the influence of social and emotional skills, and professional identity on the job satisfaction of teachers. The overall p-value is 0.000 as indicated by the f-value of 263.452. The regression,

therefore, is significant. Hence, it leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. In addition, an R² of .640 signifies that 64.0 percent of the variation in job satisfaction of teachers is explained by the predictor variables, social and emotional skills, and professional identity. while the remaining 36 percent were attributed to other factors not covered by the study. However, professional identity emerged as a significant predictor of job satisfaction of teachers with p values of $p < 0.01$ and beta-coefficients of .755. The significance on the influence of the variables to job satisfaction disclosed that professional identity particularly on the indicator's knowledge of the engagement behaviors, knowledge of the profession, attitude professional roles.

Table 6 Significance on the Influence of Independent Variables on the Job Satisfaction of Teachers

Independent Variables		Job Satisfaction			
		B	β	t	Sig.
Constant		1.354		6.485	.000
Social and Emotional Skills		-.105	-.076	-2.037	.043
Professional Identity		.755	.824	22.088	.000
R	.800				
R ²	.640				
ΔR	.638				
F	263.452				
ρ	.000				

& expertise, philosophy of the profession, professional values and interaction influences job satisfaction. On the other hand, professional identity is a good predictor of job satisfaction. Apparently, this result supports the conceptual analysis of Lim & Allida, (2021). Nonetheless, these images are continually recontextualized through the experience of teachers as job satisfaction professionals.

Similarly, this study supports the statements of his Omar et al., (2010) cited in his study. This is that a secondary school chemistry teacher underperforms his skills in three types of processes such as measurement,

interpretation and translation. Teachers show poor ability to analyze and interpret many chemical theories, mainly including diagrams and tables. you can't do that Communicate them and connect them to their lives. The extent of influence of predictor variables reveals that, social and emotional skills on the The correlation between professional identity and job satisfaction is of great significance as the study yielded a positive outcome with a significance level below the threshold of 0.05. The research indicated that almost half of the participants were impacted by their social and emotional abilities and professional identity, which was also confirmed by Reidhead's (2020)

study. In his research, Reidhead emphasized that professional identity pertains to how individuals relate to and differentiate themselves from others in their field of work, thereby constituting a form of social identity. While the definition of profession may vary, professional identity can be understood as the set of knowledge, attitudes, skills, and beliefs that are shared among members of a professional organization and pertain to the professional role undertaken by educators.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The above-mentioned findings and conclusions lead to the following recommendations. Consequently, the areas of social and emotional abilities also exhibited high outcomes in terms of the assortment of students, mastery orientation, academic self-assurance, and social proficiency, but the self-restraint and perseverance were exceptionally high.

The professional persona can uphold this elevated level. This can guarantee that educators join the profession having a comprehensive understanding of social expertise and all that it represents. Teachers frequently perceive their professional and personal identities as intertwined with one another. This focuses on knowledge of the vocation, attitude towards professional roles and expertise, philosophy of the vocation, professional principles, and interaction.

The level of job satisfaction of teachers, particularly in terms of security (income, perks, rewards for performance, recognition, promotion), work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachment, is also high among school leaders.

There is a significant correlation between emotional and social abilities and job satisfaction of teachers. Moreover, there is a significant connection between professional identity and job satisfaction of teachers.

. This is in consonance with the study of Akkerman & Meijer, 2011; Author, (2018) posited that the have Advocated a dialogue perspective in understanding how the personal and professional selves are negotiated over the course of a teaching career. A teacher's sense of professional identity is thought to be reflected in job satisfaction Moreover, social and emotional skills and professional identity are predictors of job satisfaction of teachers.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, a number of recommendations are offered. The very high level of *social and emotional skills* and high level of professional identity suggested that to sustain consistent trainings and seminars, most particularly on the novelty of the teaching strategies. The Department of Education through the school heads can spearhead the implementation. To improve the level of social and emotional skills, DepEd. officials may develop a positive self-image, take responsibility for their actions, and forge relationships with the people around them. The job satisfaction may sustain the very high level. This may be done by conducting regular evaluations, such as evaluation of leadership to be rated by supervisors, peers and self-evaluation. The results of these evaluations may be

discussed by the head of office with concerned teachers to address issues and further improve the implementation of programs of the school to achieve the organizational goals. Teachers may continue to enhance their leadership practices to support the educational success of the students as well as the improvement of the school.

As there is a shortage of educators worldwide, it is imperative to focus on teacher contentment. Teacher retention is closely linked to job satisfaction, which also plays a crucial role in the well-being of students and teachers, overall school unity, and improved teaching quality.

This suggests that social and emotional skills, as well as professional identity and job satisfaction, impacted the performance of public primary school instructors in Region XI. The professional identity and job satisfaction of teachers are built on their teaching performance. Both are critical factors that lead to high levels of internal drive, enthusiasm, and job satisfaction, and can be seen as essential elements in successful education from a performance standpoint.

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